

Asteroid Materials Mining and Recovery: Utilizing the Lunar Surface as an Asteroid Mining Platform During Early Pre Massive On-Orbit and/or Asteroid Belt Infrastructure Asteroid Mining Efforts.

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Abstract:

Recovery and exploitation of vast Asteroid and Cometary metals and minerals (etc.) resources will eventually require vast and massive infrastructure. However early efforts can take advantage of the step-wise human expansion into the solar system by leveraging Lunar resources as staging, depot and platforms for mining and recovery of the Asteroid resources. The proposed scheme is simple and is expected to be near future available even as Humanity begins to colonize the lunar surface.

To summarize the mining scheme, it is proposed that an Asteroid or cometary mass will be redirected to the lunar region and then directed to impact at some velocity onto a lunar surface 'mining area'. The then captured and deposited Asteroid materials whether impacted shallow or deep or scattered will be then easily accessible by lunar colony excavators and collectors and even processing facilities on-Luna. These resources can be exploited by the lunar colonists and even packaged for shipping to the Earth orbit and earth surface as proposed lunar resources are envisioned to be shipped to Earth.

Discussion:

Consistently and sustainably mining the asteroids and comets resources will require vast and massive resources on earth orbit, lunar orbit and surface, and in the solar system such as at the asteroid belt (eventually). This eventuality is a necessity in order to expand the resource base of Humanity yet is far into the future even as Humanity first colonizes the moon and sets up infrastructure near earth and then expanding outwards towards say the asteroid belt.

We can short-cut some of this sequential infrastructure build necessity. If so we can bring vast resource infusions into the Lunar and Earth orbits and surfaces even before such a sequential expansion.

Even as eventually first we plan to capture and bring back asteroids to orbit and to proposed processing facilities, we can use some of these concepts of capture and drag/recovery to bring these resources to an existing platform we can leverage to then mine the desired resources.

Therefore assuming that we can efficiently a) capture b) redirect c) bring back to Lunar or Earth area ...the asteroid materials, then the challenge of fragmentation or refinement or processing...as proposed in lunar or earth orbit still exist.

However as proposed here, setting aside areas of Luna for crash landing asteroid materials (large) on surface at controlled velocities, depths and scatter will then deposit these captured materials on a mining and processing platform: the Lunar surface.

Upon the Lunar surface is assumed to exist at that point a budding Lunar colony ('base') and though of limited infrastructure, yet an existing and robust infrastructure that can collect ('mine') the deposited

asteroid materials, which can then if facilities exist, can furthermore process the materials for use on Luna or for subsequent shipping from Lunar surface to Lunar orbit or to Earth orbit or to Earth surface.

Figure 1. Various Asteroid capture schemes. An Asteroid can contain \$Trillions in a specific metal or mineral and mixtures thereof.

Figure 2. A controlled crash- 'Asteroid Deposition' top: Artist rendition, bottom: An example of an (uncontrolled) crash and scatter upon a surface. The proposal here is to perform a similar deposition yet a controlled and gentler velocities and depths and scatter at a selected Lunar surface area. Subsequently and year into the future as vast infrastructure is built in orbit and at the asteroid belt this can be discontinued. In the meantime extreme and vast resources can be obtained, mined and processed.

Conclusions:

We need and wish to have the vast asteroid materials resources of metals minerals etc. To obtain these we will need to build vast infrastructure in orbit of the earth, Luna and then the asteroid belt...sequentially.

However we can bring these resources to near-future proposed lunar colony habitats and facilities simply enough. We propose to capture asteroids, redirect these to Lunar orbit and then gently or in a semi-controlled or rather directed way to deposit ('crash land') these asteroids onto as et-aside Lunar surface 'landing site' mining area.

The existing near-future lunar habitats and colonies and facilities can then simply pick up or shallow mine the scatter asteroid materials...metals alloys minerals etc....and then process them as desired.

Luna can use these or can then ship these to orbital facilities or the earth surface.

NOTE: This simple work-around proposal to deposit asteroids on the moon can significantly accelerate the access to and exploitation of asteroids and the asteroid belt vast resources, and therefore significantly accelerate Human expansion at the moon and beyond in the solar system.